

APÊNDICES

APÊNDICES

APÊNDICE I – BUSCA DOS TERMOS E ESTRATÉGIA DE PESQUISA

Data base - MEDLINE (Pubmed)	
Query – 06/06/2024	Records retrieved
<p>("Child Abuse"[All Fields] OR "abuse child"[All Fields] OR "Child Mistreatment"[All Fields] OR ("Child Abuse"[MeSH Terms] OR ("child"[All Fields] AND "abuse"[All Fields]) OR "Child Abuse"[All Fields] OR ("mistreatment"[All Fields] AND "child"[All Fields])) OR "Child Maltreatment"[All Fields] OR "maltreatment child"[All Fields] OR ("Child Abuse"[MeSH Terms] OR ("child"[All Fields] AND "abuse"[All Fields]) OR "Child Abuse"[All Fields] OR ("neglect"[All Fields] AND "experiences"[All Fields] AND "childhood"[All Fields])) OR ("Child Abuse"[MeSH Terms] OR ("child"[All Fields] AND "abuse"[All Fields]) OR "Child Abuse"[All Fields] OR ("neglect"[All Fields] AND "experience"[All Fields] AND "childhood"[All Fields])) OR "Child Neglect Experiences"[All Fields] OR ("Child Abuse"[MeSH Terms] OR ("child"[All Fields] AND "abuse"[All Fields]) OR "Child Abuse"[All Fields] OR ("child"[All Fields] AND "neglect"[All Fields] AND "experience"[All Fields])) OR ("Child Abuse"[MeSH Terms] OR ("child"[All Fields] AND "abuse"[All Fields]) OR "Child Abuse"[All Fields] OR ("experience"[All Fields] AND "child"[All Fields] AND "neglect"[All Fields])) OR ("Child Abuse"[MeSH Terms] OR ("child"[All Fields] AND "abuse"[All Fields]) OR "Child Abuse"[All Fields] OR ("neglect"[All Fields] AND "experience"[All Fields] AND "childhood"[All Fields])) OR "Childhood Neglect Experiences"[All Fields] OR ("Child Abuse"[MeSH Terms] OR ("child"[All Fields] AND "abuse"[All Fields]) OR "Child Abuse"[All Fields] OR ("childhood"[All Fields] AND "neglect"[All Fields] AND "experience"[All Fields])) OR "experience childhood neglect"[All Fields] OR "physical neglect childhood"[All Fields] OR "Childhood Physical Neglect"[All Fields] OR ("Child Abuse"[MeSH Terms] OR ("child"[All Fields] AND "abuse"[All Fields]) OR "Child Abuse"[All Fields] OR ("childhood"[All Fields] AND "physical"[All Fields] AND "neglects"[All Fields])) OR ("Child Abuse"[MeSH Terms] OR ("child"[All Fields] AND "abuse"[All Fields]) OR "Child Abuse"[All Fields] OR ("neglect"[All Fields] AND "childhood"[All Fields] AND "physical"[All Fields])) OR "child neglect physical"[All Fields] OR "neglect physical child"[All Fields] OR "Physical Child Neglect"[All Fields] OR ("Child Abuse"[MeSH Terms] OR ("child"[All Fields] AND "abuse"[All Fields]) OR "Child Abuse"[All Fields] OR ("physical"[All Fields] AND "child"[All Fields] AND "neglects"[All Fields])) OR ("Child Abuse"[MeSH Terms] OR ("child"[All Fields] AND "abuse"[All Fields]) OR "Child Abuse"[All Fields] OR ("abuse"[All Fields] AND "experiences"[All Fields] AND "childhood"[All Fields])) OR ("Child</p>	303

Abuse"[MeSH Terms] OR ("child"[All Fields] AND "abuse"[All Fields]) OR "Child Abuse"[All Fields] OR ("abuse"[All Fields] AND "experience"[All Fields] AND "childhood"[All Fields])) OR "Childhood Abuse Experience"[All Fields] OR "experience childhood abuse"[All Fields] OR "Childhood Abuse Experiences"[All Fields] OR "Child Neglect"[All Fields] OR "neglect child"[All Fields] OR "child abuse sexual"[All Fields] OR "Sexual Child Abuse"[All Fields] OR ("child abuse, sexual"[MeSH Terms] OR ("child"[All Fields] AND "abuse"[All Fields] AND "sexual"[All Fields]) OR "Sexual Child Abuse"[All Fields] OR ("molestation"[All Fields] AND "sexual"[All Fields] AND "child"[All Fields])) OR "Sexual Abuse of Child"[All Fields] OR ("child abuse, sexual"[MeSH Terms] OR ("child"[All Fields] AND "abuse"[All Fields] AND "sexual"[All Fields]) OR "Sexual Child Abuse"[All Fields] OR ("child"[All Fields] AND "molestation"[All Fields] AND "sexual"[All Fields])) OR "Sexual Child Molestation"[All Fields] OR "sexual abuse child"[All Fields] OR "abuse child sexual"[All Fields] OR "Child Sexual Abuse"[All Fields] OR "Child Molestation"[All Fields] OR ("child abuse, sexual"[MeSH Terms] OR ("child"[All Fields] AND "abuse"[All Fields] AND "sexual"[All Fields]) OR "Sexual Child Abuse"[All Fields] OR ("molestation"[All Fields] AND "child"[All Fields])))) AND ("DOMESTIC VIOLENCE"[All Fields] OR "violence domestic"[All Fields]) AND ("CHILD HEALTH SERVICES"[All Fields] OR ("CHILD HEALTH SERVICES"[MeSH Terms] OR ("child"[All Fields] AND "health"[All Fields] AND "services"[All Fields]) OR "CHILD HEALTH SERVICES"[All Fields] OR ("child"[All Fields] AND "services"[All Fields] AND "health"[All Fields])) OR "health services child"[All Fields] OR "Child Health Service"[All Fields] OR "health service child"[All Fields] OR "service child health"[All Fields] OR "services child health"[All Fields] OR "Infant Health Services"[All Fields] OR ("CHILD HEALTH SERVICES"[MeSH Terms] OR ("child"[All Fields] AND "health"[All Fields] AND "services"[All Fields]) OR "CHILD HEALTH SERVICES"[All Fields] OR ("infant"[All Fields] AND "services"[All Fields] AND "health"[All Fields])) OR "health services infant"[All Fields] OR "health service infant"[All Fields] OR "Infant Health Service"[All Fields] OR ("CHILD HEALTH SERVICES"[MeSH Terms] OR ("child"[All Fields] AND "health"[All Fields] AND "services"[All Fields]) OR "CHILD HEALTH SERVICES"[All Fields] OR ("service"[All Fields] AND "infant"[All Fields] AND "health"[All Fields])) OR ("CHILD HEALTH SERVICES"[MeSH Terms] OR ("child"[All Fields] AND "health"[All Fields] AND "services"[All Fields]) OR "CHILD HEALTH SERVICES"[All Fields] OR ("services"[All Fields] AND "infant"[All Fields] AND "health"[All Fields])) OR "HEALTH SERVICES"[All Fields] OR "Health Service"[All Fields] OR "services health"[All Fields] OR "COMMUNITY HEALTH SERVICES"[All Fields] OR "Community Health Service"[All Fields] OR "health service community"[All Fields] OR "service community health"[All Fields] OR "services community health"[All Fields] OR "health services community"[All Fields] OR "Community Health Care"[All Fields] OR "health care community"[All Fields] OR "Community Healthcare"[All Fields] OR "healthcare community"[All Fields] OR "Health Systems"[All Fields] OR "Health System"[All Fields]) AND ("EMERGENCY MEDICAL SERVICES"[All Fields] OR "emergency services medical"[All Fields] OR "emergency service medical"[All Fields] OR "Medical Emergency Service"[All Fields] OR "Medical Emergency Services"[All Fields] OR "service medical emergency"[All Fields] OR ("EMERGENCY MEDICAL

SERVICES"[MeSH Terms] OR ("emergency"[All Fields] AND "medical"[All Fields] AND "services"[All Fields]) OR "EMERGENCY MEDICAL SERVICES"[All Fields] OR ("services"[All Fields] AND "medical"[All Fields] AND "emergency"[All Fields])) OR "medical services emergency"[All Fields] OR "Emergency Medical Service"[All Fields] OR "medical service emergency"[All Fields] OR "service emergency medical"[All Fields] OR "services emergency medical"[All Fields] OR "Prehospital Emergency Care"[All Fields] OR "emergency care prehospital"[All Fields] OR "Emergicenters"[All Fields] OR "Emergicenter"[All Fields] OR "Emergency Care"[All Fields] OR "Emergency Health Services"[All Fields] OR "Emergency Health Service"[All Fields] OR "health service emergency"[All Fields] OR "health services emergency"[All Fields] OR ("EMERGENCY MEDICAL SERVICES"[MeSH Terms] OR ("emergency"[All Fields] AND "medical"[All Fields] AND "services"[All Fields]) OR "EMERGENCY MEDICAL SERVICES"[All Fields] OR ("service"[All Fields] AND "emergency"[All Fields] AND "health"[All Fields])) OR "services emergency health"[All Fields] OR "PREVENTIVE HEALTH SERVICES"[All Fields] OR "Preventive Health Care"[All Fields] OR "care preventive health"[All Fields] OR "health care preventive"[All Fields] OR "services preventive health"[All Fields] OR "Preventive Health"[All Fields] OR "health preventive"[All Fields] OR "health services preventive"[All Fields] OR "health service preventive"[All Fields] OR "Preventive Health Service"[All Fields] OR ("PREVENTIVE HEALTH SERVICES"[MeSH Terms] OR ("preventive"[All Fields] AND "health"[All Fields] AND "services"[All Fields]) OR "PREVENTIVE HEALTH SERVICES"[All Fields] OR ("service"[All Fields] AND "preventive"[All Fields] AND "health"[All Fields])) OR "Preventive Health Programs"[All Fields] OR "health program preventive"[All Fields] OR "health programs preventive"[All Fields] OR "Preventive Health Program"[All Fields] OR "program preventive health"[All Fields] OR "programs preventive health"[All Fields] OR "Preventive Programs"[All Fields] OR "Preventive Program"[All Fields] OR "program preventive"[All Fields] OR "programs preventive"[All Fields] OR "SCHOOL HEALTH SERVICES"[All Fields] OR "health service school"[All Fields] OR "School Health Service"[All Fields] OR "service school health"[All Fields] OR "school based services"[All Fields] OR "school based services"[All Fields] OR "School-Based Service"[All Fields] OR "service school based"[All Fields] OR "services school based"[All Fields] OR "services school health"[All Fields] OR "school based health services"[All Fields] OR "health service school based"[All Fields] OR "health services school based"[All Fields] OR "school based health services"[All Fields] OR "School-Based Health Service"[All Fields] OR ("SCHOOL HEALTH SERVICES"[MeSH Terms] OR ("school"[All Fields] AND "health"[All Fields] AND "services"[All Fields]) OR "SCHOOL HEALTH SERVICES"[All Fields] OR ("service"[All Fields] AND "school"[All Fields] AND "based"[All Fields] AND "health"[All Fields])) OR "services school based health"[All Fields] OR "health services school"[All Fields] OR "School Health Promotion"[All Fields] OR "health promotion school"[All Fields] OR ("SCHOOL HEALTH SERVICES"[MeSH Terms] OR ("school"[All Fields] AND "health"[All Fields] AND "services"[All Fields]) OR "SCHOOL HEALTH SERVICES"[All Fields] OR ("health"[All Fields] AND "promotions"[All Fields] AND "school"[All Fields])) OR "promotion school health"[All Fields] OR ("SCHOOL HEALTH SERVICES"[MeSH Terms] OR ("school"[All Fields] AND "health"[All Fields]

AND "services"[All Fields]) OR "SCHOOL HEALTH SERVICES"[All Fields] OR ("promotions"[All Fields] AND "school"[All Fields] AND "health"[All Fields])) OR ("SCHOOL HEALTH SERVICES"[MeSH Terms] OR ("school"[All Fields] AND "health"[All Fields] AND "services"[All Fields]) OR "SCHOOL HEALTH SERVICES"[All Fields] OR ("school"[All Fields] AND "health"[All Fields] AND "promotions"[All Fields])) OR "CHILD CARE"[All Fields] OR "care child"[All Fields] OR "Puericulture"[All Fields] OR "Child Day Care"[All Fields] OR "day care child"[All Fields] OR "CHILD DAY CARE CENTERS"[All Fields] OR "Daycare Centers for Children"[All Fields] OR "Child Daycare Centers"[All Fields] OR "Child Daycare Center"[All Fields] OR "Day Care Centers for Children"[All Fields] OR "Child Advocacy"[All Fields])	
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Data base – EMBASE	
Query	Records retrieved
('child abuse' OR 'abuse, child' OR 'child mistreatment' OR 'mistreatment, child' OR 'child maltreatment' OR 'maltreatment, child' OR 'neglect experiences, childhood' OR 'neglect experience, childhood' OR 'child neglect experiences' OR 'child neglect experience' OR 'experience, child neglect' OR 'neglect experience, child' OR 'childhood neglect experiences' OR 'childhood neglect experience' OR 'experience, childhood neglect' OR 'physical neglect, childhood' OR 'childhood physical neglect' OR 'childhood physical neglects' OR 'neglect, childhood physical' OR 'child neglect, physical' OR 'neglect, physical child' OR 'physical child neglect' OR 'physical child neglects' OR 'abuse experiences, childhood' OR 'abuse experience, childhood' OR 'childhood abuse experience' OR 'experience, childhood abuse' OR 'childhood abuse experiences' OR 'child neglect' OR 'neglect, child' OR 'child abuse, sexual' OR 'sexual child abuse' OR 'molestation, sexual, child' OR 'sexual abuse of child' OR 'child molestation, sexual' OR 'sexual child molestation' OR 'sexual abuse, child' OR 'abuse, child sexual' OR 'child sexual abuse' OR 'child molestation' OR 'molestation, child') AND ('domestic violence' OR 'violence, domestic') AND ('child health services' OR 'child services, health' OR 'health services, child' OR 'child health service' OR 'health service, child' OR 'service, child health' OR 'services, child health' OR 'infant health services' OR 'infant services, health' OR 'health services, infant' OR 'health service, infant' OR 'infant health service' OR 'service, infant health' OR 'services, infant health' OR 'health services' OR 'health service' OR 'services, health' OR 'community health services' OR 'community health service' OR 'health service, community' OR 'service, community health' OR 'services, community health' OR 'health services, community' OR 'community health care' OR 'health care, community' OR 'community healthcare' OR 'healthcare, community' OR 'health systems' OR 'health system') AND ('emergency medical services' OR 'emergency services, medical' OR 'emergency service, medical' OR 'medical emergency service' OR 'medical emergency services' OR 'service, medical emergency' OR 'services, medical emergency' OR 'medical services, emergency' OR 'emergency medical service' OR 'medical service, emergency' OR 'service, emergency medical' OR 'services, emergency medical' OR 'prehospital emergency care' OR 'emergency care, prehospital' OR 'emergicenters' OR 'emergicenter' OR	82

<p>'emergency care' OR 'emergency health services' OR 'emergency health service' OR 'health service, emergency' OR 'health services, emergency' OR 'service, emergency health' OR 'services, emergency health' OR 'preventive health services' OR 'preventive health care' OR 'care, preventive health' OR 'health care, preventive' OR 'services, preventive health' OR 'preventive health' OR 'health, preventive' OR 'health services, preventive' OR 'health service, preventive' OR 'preventive health service' OR 'service, preventive health' OR 'preventive health programs' OR 'health program, preventive' OR 'health programs, preventive' OR 'preventive health program' OR 'program, preventive health' OR 'programs, preventive health' OR 'preventive programs' OR 'preventive program' OR 'program, preventive' OR 'programs, preventive' OR 'school health services' OR 'health service, school' OR 'school health service' OR 'service, school health' OR 'school-based services' OR 'school based services' OR 'school-based service' OR 'service, school-based' OR 'services, school-based' OR 'services, school health' OR 'school-based health services' OR 'health service, school-based' OR 'health services, school-based' OR 'school based health services' OR 'school-based health service' OR 'service, school-based health' OR 'services, school-based health' OR 'health services, school' OR 'school health promotion' OR 'health promotion, school' OR 'health promotions, school' OR 'promotion, school health' OR 'promotions, school health' OR 'school health promotions' OR 'child care' OR 'care, child' OR 'puericulture' OR 'child day care' OR 'day care, child' OR 'child day care centers' OR 'daycare centers for children' OR 'child daycare centers' OR 'child daycare center' OR 'day care centers for children' OR 'child advocacy')</p>	
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Data base – BVS (LILACs)	
Query	Records retrieved
<p>("Child Abuse" OR "Abuse, Child" OR "Child Mistreatment" OR "Mistreatment, Child" OR "Child Maltreatment" OR "Maltreatment, Child" OR "Neglect Experiences, Childhood" OR "Neglect Experience, Childhood" OR "Child Neglect Experiences" OR "Child Neglect Experience" OR "Experience, Child Neglect" OR "Neglect Experience, Child" OR "Childhood Neglect Experiences" OR "Childhood Neglect Experience" OR "Experience, Childhood Neglect" OR "Physical Neglect, Childhood" OR "Childhood Physical Neglect" OR "Childhood Physical Neglects" OR "Neglect, Childhood Physical" OR "Child Neglect, Physical" OR "Neglect, Physical Child" OR "Physical Child Neglect" OR "Physical Child Neglects" OR "Abuse Experiences, Childhood" OR "Abuse Experience, Childhood" OR "Childhood Abuse Experience" OR "Experience, Childhood Abuse" OR "Childhood Abuse Experiences" OR "Child Neglect" OR "Neglect, Child" OR "Child Abuse, Sexual" OR "Sexual Child Abuse" OR "Molestation, Sexual, Child" OR "Sexual Abuse of Child" OR "Child Molestation, Sexual" OR "Sexual Child Molestation" OR "Sexual Abuse, Child" OR "Abuse, Child Sexual" OR "Child Sexual Abuse" OR "Child Molestation" OR "Molestation, Child") AND ("DOMESTIC VIOLENCE" OR "Violence, Domestic") AND ("CHILD HEALTH SERVICES" OR "Child Services, Health" OR "Health Services, Child" OR "Child Health Service" OR "Health Service, Child" OR "Service, Child Health" OR "Services, Child Health" OR "Infant</p>	10

<p>Health Services" OR "Infant Services, Health" OR "Health Services, Infant" OR "Health Service, Infant" OR "Infant Health Service" OR "Service, Infant Health" OR "Services, Infant Health" OR "HEALTH SERVICES" OR "Health Service" OR "Services, Health" OR "COMMUNITY HEALTH SERVICES" OR "Community Health Service" OR "Health Service, Community" OR "Service, Community Health" OR "Services, Community Health" OR "Health Services, Community" OR "Community Health Care" OR "Health Care, Community" OR "Community Healthcare" OR "Healthcare, Community" OR "Health Systems" OR "Health System") AND ("EMERGENCY MEDICAL SERVICES" OR "Emergency Services, Medical" OR "Emergency Service, Medical" OR "Medical Emergency Service" OR "Medical Emergency Services" OR "Service, Medical Emergency" OR "Services, Medical Emergency" OR "Medical Services, Emergency" OR "Emergency Medical Service" OR "Medical Service, Emergency" OR "Service, Emergency Medical" OR "Services, Emergency Medical" OR "Prehospital Emergency Care" OR "Emergency Care, Prehospital" OR "Emergicenters" OR "Emergicenter" OR "Emergency Care" OR "Emergency Health Services" OR "Emergency Health Service" OR "Health Service, Emergency" OR "Health Services, Emergency" OR "Service, Emergency Health" OR "Services, Emergency Health" OR "PREVENTIVE HEALTH SERVICES" OR "Preventive Health Care" OR "Care, Preventive Health" OR "Health Care, Preventive" OR "Services, Preventive Health" OR "Preventive Health" OR "Health, Preventive" OR "Health Services, Preventive" OR "Health Service, Preventive" OR "Preventive Health Service" OR "Service, Preventive Health" OR "Preventive Health Programs" OR "Health Program, Preventive" OR "Health Programs, Preventive" OR "Preventive Health Program" OR "Program, Preventive Health" OR "Programs, Preventive Health" OR "Preventive Programs" OR "Preventive Program" OR "Program, Preventive" OR "Programs, Preventive" OR "SCHOOL HEALTH SERVICES" OR "Health Service, School" OR "School Health Service" OR "Service, School Health" OR "School-Based Services" OR "School Based Services" OR "School-Based Service" OR "Service, School-Based" OR "Services, School-Based" OR "Services, School Health" OR "School-Based Health Services" OR "Health Service, School-Based" OR "Health Services, School-Based" OR "School Based Health Services" OR "School-Based Health Service" OR "Service, School-Based Health" OR "Services, School-Based Health" OR "Health Services, School" OR "School Health Promotion" OR "Health Promotion, School" OR "Health Promotions, School" OR "Promotion, School Health" OR "Promotions, School Health" OR "School Health Promotions" OR "CHILD CARE" OR "Care, Child" OR "Puericulture" OR "Child Day Care" OR "Day Care, Child" OR "CHILD DAY CARE CENTERS" OR "Daycare Centers for Children" OR "Child Daycare Centers" OR "Child Daycare Center" OR "Day Care Centers for Children" OR "Child Advocacy") AND (db:("LILACS"))</p>	
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Data base – BVS (BDNF)	
Query	Records retrieved
("Child Abuse" OR "Abuse, Child" OR "Child Mistreatment" OR "Mistreatment,	0

Child" OR "Child Maltreatment" OR "Maltreatment, Child" OR "Neglect Experiences, Childhood" OR "Neglect Experience, Childhood" OR "Child Neglect Experiences" OR "Child Neglect Experience" OR "Experience, Child Neglect" OR "Neglect Experience, Child" OR "Childhood Neglect Experiences" OR "Childhood Neglect Experience" OR "Experience, Childhood Neglect" OR "Physical Neglect, Childhood" OR "Childhood Physical Neglect" OR "Childhood Physical Neglects" OR "Neglect, Childhood Physical" OR "Child Neglect, Physical" OR "Neglect, Physical Child" OR "Physical Child Neglect" OR "Physical Child Neglects" OR "Abuse Experiences, Childhood" OR "Abuse Experience, Childhood" OR "Childhood Abuse Experience" OR "Experience, Childhood Abuse" OR "Childhood Abuse Experiences" OR "Child Neglect" OR "Neglect, Child" OR "Child Abuse, Sexual" OR "Sexual Child Abuse" OR "Molestation, Sexual, Child" OR "Sexual Abuse of Child" OR "Child Molestation, Sexual" OR "Sexual Child Molestation" OR "Sexual Abuse, Child" OR "Abuse, Child Sexual" OR "Child Sexual Abuse" OR "Child Molestation" OR "Molestation, Child") AND ("DOMESTIC VIOLENCE" OR "Violence, Domestic") AND ("CHILD HEALTH SERVICES" OR "Child Services, Health" OR "Health Services, Child" OR "Child Health Service" OR "Health Service, Child" OR "Service, Child Health" OR "Services, Child Health" OR "Infant Health Services" OR "Infant Services, Health" OR "Health Services, Infant" OR "Health Service, Infant" OR "Infant Health Service" OR "Service, Infant Health" OR "Services, Infant Health" OR "HEALTH SERVICES" OR "Health Service" OR "Services, Health" OR "COMMUNITY HEALTH SERVICES" OR "Community Health Service" OR "Health Service, Community" OR "Service, Community Health" OR "Services, Community Health" OR "Health Services, Community" OR "Community Health Care" OR "Health Care, Community" OR "Community Healthcare" OR "Healthcare, Community" OR "Health Systems" OR "Health System") AND ("EMERGENCY MEDICAL SERVICES" OR "Emergency Services, Medical" OR "Emergency Service, Medical" OR "Medical Emergency Service" OR "Medical Emergency Services" OR "Service, Medical Emergency" OR "Services, Medical Emergency" OR "Medical Services, Emergency" OR "Emergency Medical Service" OR "Medical Service, Emergency" OR "Service, Emergency Medical" OR "Services, Emergency Medical" OR "Prehospital Emergency Care" OR "Emergency Care, Prehospital" OR "Emergicenters" OR "Emergicenter" OR "Emergency Care" OR "Emergency Health Services" OR "Emergency Health Service" OR "Health Service, Emergency" OR "Health Services, Emergency" OR "Service, Emergency Health" OR "Services, Emergency Health" OR "PREVENTIVE HEALTH SERVICES" OR "Preventive Health Care" OR "Care, Preventive Health" OR "Health Care, Preventive" OR "Services, Preventive Health" OR "Preventive Health" OR "Health, Preventive" OR "Health Services, Preventive" OR "Health Service, Preventive" OR "Preventive Health Service" OR "Service, Preventive Health" OR "Preventive Health Programs" OR "Health Program, Preventive" OR "Health Programs, Preventive" OR "Preventive Health Program" OR "Program, Preventive Health" OR "Programs, Preventive Health" OR "Preventive Programs" OR "Preventive Program" OR "Program, Preventive" OR "Programs, Preventive" OR "SCHOOL HEALTH SERVICES" OR "Health Service, School" OR "School Health Service" OR "Service, School Health" OR "School-Based Services" OR "School Based Services" OR "School-Based Service" OR "Service, School-Based" OR "Services, School-Based" OR "Services, School

Health" OR "School-Based Health Services" OR "Health Service, School-Based" OR "Health Services, School-Based" OR "School Based Health Services" OR "School-Based Health Service" OR "Service, School-Based Health" OR "Services, School-Based Health" OR "Health Services, School" OR "School Health Promotion" OR "Health Promotion, School" OR "Health Promotions, School" OR "Promotion, School Health" OR "Promotions, School Health" OR "School Health Promotions" OR "CHILD CARE" OR "Care, Child" OR "Puericulture" OR "Child Day Care" OR "Day Care, Child" OR "CHILD DAY CARE CENTERS" OR "Daycare Centers for Children" OR "Child Daycare Centers" OR "Child Daycare Center" OR "Day Care Centers for Children" OR "Child Advocacy") AND (db:("BDENF"))	
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Data base – CINAHL	
Query	Records retrieved
("Child Abuse" OR "Abuse, Child" OR "Child Mistreatment" OR "Mistreatment, Child" OR "Child Maltreatment" OR "Maltreatment, Child" OR "Neglect Experiences, Childhood" OR "Neglect Experience, Childhood" OR "Child Neglect Experiences" OR "Child Neglect Experience" OR "Experience, Child Neglect" OR "Neglect Experience, Child" OR "Childhood Neglect Experiences" OR "Childhood Neglect Experience" OR "Experience, Childhood Neglect" OR "Physical Neglect, Childhood" OR "Childhood Physical Neglect" OR "Childhood Physical Neglects" OR "Neglect, Childhood Physical" OR "Child Neglect, Physical" OR "Neglect, Physical Child" OR "Physical Child Neglect" OR "Physical Child Neglects" OR "Abuse Experiences, Childhood" OR "Abuse Experience, Childhood" OR "Childhood Abuse Experience" OR "Experience, Childhood Abuse" OR "Childhood Abuse Experiences" OR "Child Neglect" OR "Neglect, Child" OR "Child Abuse, Sexual" OR "Sexual Child Abuse" OR "Molestation, Sexual, Child" OR "Sexual Abuse of Child" OR "Child Molestation, Sexual" OR "Sexual Child Molestation" OR "Sexual Abuse, Child" OR "Abuse, Child Sexual" OR "Child Sexual Abuse" OR "Child Molestation" OR "Molestation, Child") AND ("DOMESTIC VIOLENCE" OR "Violence, Domestic") AND ("CHILD HEALTH SERVICES" OR "Child Services, Health" OR "Health Services, Child" OR "Child Health Service" OR "Health Service, Child" OR "Service, Child Health" OR "Services, Child Health" OR "Infant Health Services" OR "Infant Services, Health" OR "Health Services, Infant" OR "Health Service, Infant" OR "Infant Health Service" OR "Service, Infant Health" OR "Services, Infant Health" OR "HEALTH SERVICES" OR "Health Service" OR "Services, Health" OR "COMMUNITY HEALTH SERVICES" OR "Community Health Service" OR "Health Service, Community" OR "Service, Community Health" OR "Services, Community Health" OR "Health Services, Community" OR "Community Health Care" OR "Health Care, Community" OR "Community Healthcare" OR "Healthcare, Community" OR "Health Systems" OR "Health System") AND ("EMERGENCY MEDICAL SERVICES" OR "Emergency Services, Medical" OR "Emergency Service, Medical" OR "Medical Emergency Service" OR "Medical Emergency Services" OR "Service, Medical Emergency" OR "Services,	20

<p>Medical Emergency" OR "Medical Services, Emergency" OR "Emergency Medical Service" OR "Medical Service, Emergency" OR "Service, Emergency Medical" OR "Services, Emergency Medical" OR "Prehospital Emergency Care" OR "Emergency Care, Prehospital" OR "Emergicenters" OR "Emergicenter" OR "Emergency Care" OR "Emergency Health Services" OR "Emergency Health Service" OR "Health Service, Emergency" OR "Health Services, Emergency" OR "Service, Emergency Health" OR "Services, Emergency Health" OR "PREVENTIVE HEALTH SERVICES" OR "Preventive Health Care" OR "Care, Preventive Health" OR "Health Care, Preventive" OR "Services, Preventive Health" OR "Preventive Health" OR "Health, Preventive" OR "Health Services, Preventive" OR "Health Service, Preventive" OR "Preventive Health Service" OR "Service, Preventive Health" OR "Preventive Health Programs" OR "Health Program, Preventive" OR "Health Programs, Preventive" OR "Preventive Health Program" OR "Program, Preventive Health" OR "Programs, Preventive Health" OR "Preventive Programs" OR "Preventive Program" OR "Program, Preventive" OR "Programs, Preventive" OR "SCHOOL HEALTH SERVICES" OR "Health Service, School" OR "School Health Service" OR "Service, School Health" OR "School-Based Services" OR "School Based Services" OR "School-Based Service" OR "Service, School-Based" OR "Services, School-Based" OR "Services, School Health" OR "School-Based Health Services" OR "Health Service, School-Based" OR "Health Services, School-Based" OR "School Based Health Services" OR "School-Based Health Service" OR "Service, School-Based Health" OR "Services, School-Based Health" OR "Health Services, School" OR "School Health Promotion" OR "Health Promotion, School" OR "Health Promotions, School" OR "Promotion, School Health" OR "Promotions, School Health" OR "School Health Promotions" OR "CHILD CARE" OR "Care, Child" OR "Puericulture" OR "Child Day Care" OR "Day Care, Child" OR "CHILD DAY CARE CENTERS" OR "Daycare Centers for Children" OR "Child Daycare Centers" OR "Child Daycare Center" OR "Day Care Centers for Children" OR "Child Advocacy")</p>	
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Data base – SciELO	
Query (sem o grupo do INTERSETORIAL)	Records retrieved
<p>("Child Abuse" OR "Abuse, Child" OR "Child Mistreatment" OR "Mistreatment, Child" OR "Child Maltreatment" OR "Maltreatment, Child" OR "Neglect Experiences, Childhood" OR "Neglect Experience, Childhood" OR "Child Neglect Experiences" OR "Child Neglect Experience" OR "Experience, Child Neglect" OR "Neglect Experience, Child" OR "Childhood Neglect Experiences" OR "Childhood Neglect Experience" OR "Experience, Childhood Neglect" OR "Physical Neglect, Childhood" OR "Childhood Physical Neglect" OR "Childhood Physical Neglects" OR "Neglect, Childhood Physical" OR "Child Neglect, Physical" OR "Neglect, Physical Child" OR "Physical Child Neglect" OR "Physical Child Neglects" OR "Abuse Experiences, Childhood" OR "Abuse Experience, Childhood" OR "Childhood Abuse Experience" OR "Experience, Childhood Abuse" OR "Childhood Abuse Experiences" OR "Child Neglect" OR "Neglect, Child" OR "Child Abuse, Sexual" OR "Sexual Child Abuse" OR</p>	6

<p>"Molestation, Sexual, Child" OR "Sexual Abuse of Child" OR "Child Molestation, Sexual" OR "Sexual Child Molestation" OR "Sexual Abuse, Child" OR "Abuse, Child Sexual" OR "Child Sexual Abuse" OR "Child Molestation" OR "Molestation, Child") AND ("DOMESTIC VIOLENCE" OR "Violence, Domestic") AND ("CHILD HEALTH SERVICES" OR "Child Services, Health" OR "Health Services, Child" OR "Child Health Service" OR "Health Service, Child" OR "Service, Child Health" OR "Services, Child Health" OR "Infant Health Services" OR "Infant Services, Health" OR "Health Services, Infant" OR "Health Service, Infant" OR "Infant Health Service" OR "Service, Infant Health" OR "Services, Infant Health" OR "HEALTH SERVICES" OR "Health Service" OR "Services, Health" OR "COMMUNITY HEALTH SERVICES" OR "Community Health Service" OR "Health Service, Community" OR "Service, Community Health" OR "Services, Community Health" OR "Health Services, Community" OR "Community Health Care" OR "Health Care, Community" OR "Community Healthcare" OR "Healthcare, Community" OR "Health Systems" OR "Health System")</p>	
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Data base – COCHRANE	
Query (sem o grupo do INTERSETORIAL)	Records retrieved
<p>"Child Abuse" OR "Abuse, Child" OR "Child Mistreatment" OR "Mistreatment, Child" OR "Child Maltreatment" OR "Maltreatment, Child" OR "Neglect Experiences, Childhood" OR "Neglect Experience, Childhood" OR "Child Neglect Experiences" OR "Child Neglect Experience" OR "Experience, Child Neglect" OR "Neglect Experience, Child" OR "Childhood Neglect Experiences" OR "Childhood Neglect Experience" OR "Experience, Childhood Neglect" OR "Physical Neglect, Childhood" OR "Childhood Physical Neglect" OR "Childhood Physical Neglects" OR "Neglect, Childhood Physical" OR "Child Neglect, Physical" OR "Neglect, Physical Child" OR "Physical Child Neglect" OR "Physical Child Neglects" OR "Abuse Experiences, Childhood" OR "Abuse Experience, Childhood" OR "Childhood Abuse Experience" OR "Experience, Childhood Abuse" OR "Childhood Abuse Experiences" OR "Child Neglect" OR "Neglect, Child" OR "Child Abuse, Sexual" OR "Sexual Child Abuse" OR "Molestation, Sexual, Child" OR "Sexual Abuse of Child" OR "Child Molestation, Sexual" OR "Sexual Child Molestation" OR "Sexual Abuse, Child" OR "Abuse, Child Sexual" OR "Child Sexual Abuse" OR "Child Molestation" OR "Molestation, Child" in All Text AND "DOMESTIC VIOLENCE" OR "Violence, Domestic" in All Text AND "CHILD HEALTH SERVICES" OR "Child Services, Health" OR "Health Services, Child" OR "Child Health Service" OR "Health Service, Child" OR "Service, Child Health" OR "Services, Child Health" OR "Infant Health Services" OR "Infant Services, Health" OR "Health Services, Infant" OR "Health Service, Infant" OR "Infant Health Service" OR "Service, Infant Health" OR "Services, Infant Health" OR "HEALTH SERVICES" OR "Health Service" OR "Services, Health" OR "COMMUNITY HEALTH SERVICES" OR "Community Health Service" OR "Health Service, Community" OR "Service, Community Health" OR "Services, Community Health" OR "Health Services, Community" OR "Community Health Care" OR</p>	26

"Health Care, Community" OR "Community Healthcare" OR "Healthcare, Community" OR "Health Systems" OR "Health System" in All Text - (Word variations have been searched)	
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Data base – SCOPUS	
Query	Records retrieved
(TITLE-ABS-KEY ("child abuse" OR "abuse, child" OR "child mistreatment" OR "mistreatment, child" OR "child maltreatment" OR "maltreatment, child" OR "neglect experiences, childhood" OR "neglect experience, childhood" OR "child neglect experiences" OR "child neglect experience" OR "experience, child neglect" OR "neglect experience, child" OR "childhood neglect experiences" OR "childhood neglect experience" OR "experience, childhood neglect" OR "physical neglect, childhood" OR "childhood physical neglect" OR "childhood physical neglects" OR "neglect, childhood physical" OR "child neglect, physical" OR "neglect, physical child" OR "physical child neglect" OR "physical child neglects" OR "abuse experiences, childhood" OR "abuse experience, childhood" OR "childhood abuse experience" OR "experience, childhood abuse" OR "childhood abuse experiences" OR "child neglect" OR "neglect, child" OR "child abuse, sexual" OR "sexual child abuse" OR "molestation, sexual, child" OR "sexual abuse of child" OR "child molestation, sexual" OR "sexual child molestation" OR "sexual abuse, child" OR "abuse, child sexual" OR "child sexual abuse" OR "child molestation" OR "molestation, child") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ("domestic violence" OR "violence, domestic") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ("child health services" OR "child services, health" OR "health services, child" OR "child health service" OR "health service, child" OR "service, child health" OR "services, child health" OR "infant health services" OR "infant services, health" OR "health services, infant" OR "health service, infant" OR "infant health service" OR "service, infant health" OR "services, infant health" OR "health services" OR "health service" OR "services, health" OR "community health services" OR "community health service" OR "health service, community" OR "service, community health" OR "services, community health" OR "health services, community" OR "community health care" OR "health care, community" OR "community healthcare" OR "healthcare, community" OR "health systems" OR "health system") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ("emergency medical services" OR "emergency services, medical" OR "emergency service, medical" OR "medical emergency service" OR "medical emergency services" OR "service, medical emergency" OR "services, medical emergency" OR "medical services, emergency" OR "emergency medical service" OR "medical service, emergency" OR "service, emergency medical" OR "services, emergency medical" OR "prehospital emergency care" OR "emergency care, prehospital" OR "emergicenters" OR "emergicenter" OR "emergency care" OR "emergency health services" OR "emergency health service" OR "health service, emergency" OR "health services, emergency" OR "service, emergency health" OR "services, emergency health" OR "preventive health services" OR "preventive health care" OR "care, preventive health" OR "health care, preventive" OR "services, preventive health" OR "preventive health" OR "health, preventive" OR "health	104

<p>services, preventive" OR "health service, preventive" OR "preventive health service" OR "service, preventive health" OR "preventive health programs" OR "health program, preventive" OR "health programs, preventive" OR "preventive health program" OR "program, preventive health" OR "programs, preventive health" OR "preventive programs" OR "preventive program" OR "program, preventive" OR "programs, preventive" OR "school health services" OR "health service, school" OR "school health service" OR "service, school health" OR "school-based services" OR "school based services" OR "school-based service" OR "service, school-based" OR "services, school-based" OR "services, school health" OR "school-based health services" OR "health service, school-based" OR "health services, school-based" OR "school based health services" OR "school-based health service" OR "service, school-based health" OR "services, school-based health" OR "health services, school" OR "school health promotion" OR "health promotion, school" OR "health promotions, school" OR "promotion, school health" OR "promotions, school health" OR "school health promotions" OR "child care" OR "care, child" OR "puericulture" OR "child day care" OR "day care, child" OR "child day care centers" OR "daycare centers for children" OR "child daycare centers" OR "child daycare center" OR "day care centers for children" OR "child advocacy"))</p>	
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Data base – Web of Science	
Query (sem o grupo do INTERSETORIAL)	Records retrieved
<p>"Child Abuse" OR "Abuse, Child" OR "Child Mistreatment" OR "Mistreatment, Child" OR "Child Maltreatment" OR "Maltreatment, Child" OR "Neglect Experiences, Childhood" OR "Neglect Experience, Childhood" OR "Child Neglect Experiences" OR "Child Neglect Experience" OR "Experience, Child Neglect" OR "Neglect Experience, Child" OR "Childhood Neglect Experiences" OR "Childhood Neglect Experience" OR "Experience, Childhood Neglect" OR "Physical Neglect, Childhood" OR "Childhood Physical Neglect" OR "Childhood Physical Neglects" OR "Neglect, Childhood Physical" OR "Child Neglect, Physical" OR "Neglect, Physical Child" OR "Physical Child Neglect" OR "Physical Child Neglects" OR "Abuse Experiences, Childhood" OR "Abuse Experience, Childhood" OR "Childhood Abuse Experience" OR "Experience, Childhood Abuse" OR "Childhood Abuse Experiences" OR "Child Neglect" OR "Neglect, Child" OR "Child Abuse, Sexual" OR "Sexual Child Abuse" OR "Molestation, Sexual, Child" OR "Sexual Abuse of Child" OR "Child Molestation, Sexual" OR "Sexual Child Molestation" OR "Sexual Abuse, Child" OR "Abuse, Child Sexual" OR "Child Sexual Abuse" OR "Child Molestation" OR "Molestation, Child" (All Fields) and "DOMESTIC VIOLENCE" OR "Violence, Domestic" (All Fields) and "CHILD HEALTH SERVICES" OR "Child Services, Health" OR "Health Services, Child" OR "Child Health Service" OR "Health Service, Child" OR "Service, Child Health" OR "Services, Child Health" OR "Infant Health Services" OR "Infant Services, Health" OR "Health Services, Infant" OR "Health Service, Infant" OR "Infant Health Service" OR "Service, Infant Health" OR "Services, Infant Health" OR "HEALTH SERVICES" OR "Health Service" OR "Services, Health" OR "COMMUNITY</p>	92

HEALTH SERVICES" OR "Community Health Service" OR "Health Service, Community" OR "Service, Community Health" OR "Services, Community Health" OR "Health Services, Community" OR "Community Health Care" OR "Health Care, Community" OR "Community Healthcare" OR "Healthcare, Community" OR "Health Systems" OR "Health System" (All Fields)	
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Data base – Open Grey	
Query	Records retrieved
"Child Abuse" OR "Abuse, Child" OR "Child Mistreatment" OR "Mistreatment, Child" OR "Child Maltreatment" OR "Maltreatment, Child" OR "Neglect Experiences, Childhood" OR "Neglect Experience, Childhood" OR "Child Neglect Experiences" OR "Child Neglect Experience" OR "Experience, Child Neglect" OR "Neglect Experience, Child" OR "Childhood Neglect Experiences" OR "Childhood Neglect Experience" OR "Experience, Childhood Neglect" OR "Physical Neglect, Childhood" OR "Childhood Physical Neglect" OR "Childhood Physical Neglects" OR "Neglect, Childhood Physical" OR "Child Neglect, Physical" OR "Neglect, Physical Child" OR "Physical Child Neglect" OR "Physical Child Neglects" OR "Abuse Experiences, Childhood" OR "Abuse Experience, Childhood" OR "Childhood Abuse Experience" OR "Experience, Childhood Abuse" OR "Childhood Abuse Experiences" OR "Child Neglect" OR "Neglect, Child" OR "Child Abuse, Sexual" OR "Sexual Child Abuse" OR "Molestation, Sexual, Child" OR "Sexual Abuse of Child" OR "Child Molestation, Sexual" OR "Sexual Child Molestation" OR "Sexual Abuse, Child" OR "Abuse, Child Sexual" OR "Child Sexual Abuse" OR "Child Molestation" OR "Molestation, Child"	0

Data base – Proquest	
Query	Records retrieved
noft("Child Abuse" OR "Abuse, Child" OR "Child Mistreatment" OR "Mistreatment, Child" OR "Child Maltreatment" OR "Maltreatment, Child" OR "Neglect Experiences, Childhood" OR "Neglect Experience, Childhood" OR "Child Neglect Experiences" OR "Child Neglect Experience" OR "Experience, Child Neglect" OR "Neglect Experience, Child" OR "Childhood Neglect Experiences" OR "Childhood Neglect Experience" OR "Experience, Childhood Neglect" OR "Physical Neglect, Childhood" OR "Childhood Physical Neglect" OR "Childhood Physical Neglects" OR "Neglect, Childhood Physical" OR "Child Neglect, Physical" OR "Neglect, Physical Child" OR "Physical Child Neglect" OR "Physical Child Neglects" OR "Abuse Experiences, Childhood" OR "Abuse Experience, Childhood" OR "Childhood Abuse Experience" OR "Experience, Childhood Abuse" OR "Childhood Abuse Experiences" OR "Child Neglect" OR "Neglect, Child" OR "Child Abuse, Sexual" OR "Sexual Child Abuse" OR "Molestation, Sexual, Child" OR "Sexual Abuse of Child" OR "Child Molestation, Sexual" OR "Sexual Child Molestation" OR "Sexual Abuse, Child"	1

OR "Abuse, Child Sexual" OR "Child Sexual Abuse" OR "Child Molestation" OR "Molestation, Child") AND noft("DOMESTIC VIOLENCE" OR "Violence, Domestic") AND noft("CHILD HEALTH SERVICES" OR "Child Services, Health" OR "Health Services, Child" OR "Child Health Service" OR "Health Service, Child" OR "Service, Child Health" OR "Services, Child Health" OR "Infant Health Services" OR "Infant Services, Health" OR "Health Services, Infant" OR "Health Service, Infant" OR "Infant Health Service" OR "Service, Infant Health" OR "Services, Infant Health" OR "HEALTH SERVICES" OR "Health Service" OR "Services, Health" OR "COMMUNITY HEALTH SERVICES" OR "Community Health Service" OR "Health Service, Community" OR "Service, Community Health" OR "Services, Community Health" OR "Health Services, Community" OR "Community Health Care" OR "Health Care, Community" OR "Community Healthcare" OR "Healthcare, Community" OR "Health Systems" OR "Health System") AND noft("EMERGENCY MEDICAL SERVICES" OR "Emergency Services, Medical" OR "Emergency Service, Medical" OR "Medical Emergency Service" OR "Medical Emergency Services" OR "Service, Medical Emergency" OR "Services, Medical Emergency" OR "Medical Services, Emergency" OR "Emergency Medical Service" OR "Medical Service, Emergency" OR "Service, Emergency Medical" OR "Services, Emergency Medical" OR "Prehospital Emergency Care" OR "Emergency Care, Prehospital" OR "Emergicenters" OR "Emergicenter" OR "Emergency Care" OR "Emergency Health Services" OR "Emergency Health Service" OR "Health Service, Emergency" OR "Health Services, Emergency" OR "Service, Emergency Health" OR "Services, Emergency Health" OR "PREVENTIVE HEALTH SERVICES" OR "Preventive Health Care" OR "Care, Preventive Health" OR "Health Care, Preventive" OR "Services, Preventive Health" OR "Preventive Health" OR "Health, Preventive" OR "Health Services, Preventive" OR "Health Service, Preventive" OR "Preventive Health Service" OR "Service, Preventive Health" OR "Preventive Health Programs" OR "Health Program, Preventive" OR "Health Programs, Preventive" OR "Preventive Health Program" OR "Program, Preventive Health" OR "Programs, Preventive Health" OR "Preventive Programs" OR "Preventive Program" OR "Program, Preventive" OR "Programs, Preventive" OR "SCHOOL HEALTH SERVICES" OR "Health Service, School" OR "School Health Service" OR "Service, School Health" OR "School-Based Services" OR "School Based Services" OR "School-Based Service" OR "Service, School-Based" OR "Services, School-Based" OR "Services, School Health" OR "School-Based Health Services" OR "Health Service, School-Based" OR "Health Services, School-Based" OR "School Based Health Services" OR "School-Based Health Service" OR "Service, School-Based Health" OR "Services, School-Based Health" OR "Health Services, School" OR "School Health Promotion" OR "Health Promotion, School" OR "Health Promotions, School" OR "Promotion, School Health" OR "Promotions, School Health" OR "School Health Promotions" OR "CHILD CARE" OR "Care, Child" OR "Puericulture" OR "Child Day Care" OR "Day Care, Child" OR "CHILD DAY CARE CENTERS" OR "Daycare Centers for Children" OR "Child Daycare Centers" OR "Child Daycare Center" OR "Day Care Centers for Children" OR "Child Advocacy")

APÊNDICE II – FONTES EXCLUÍDAS APÓS REVISÃO DO TEXTO COMPLETO. SÃO PAULO, 2025

1. Asiegbunam N. Introducing routine enquiry about domestic violence in a paediatric setting. Archives of disease in childhood Education and practice edition. Fevereiro de 2018;103(1):41–2.

Motivo da exclusão: Artigo incompleto, sem metodologia, sem discussão, resultado e/ou conclusão.

2. Banks D, Landsverk J, Wang K. Changing policy and practice in the child welfare system through collaborative efforts to identify and respond effectively to family violence. Journal of interpersonal violence. Julho de 2008;23(7):903–32.

Motivo da exclusão: O resumo está mau elaborado, utiliza um guia de reflexão e história e não tem Conclusão.

3. Crouch E, Radcliff E, Nelson J, Strompolis M, Martin A. The experience of adverse childhood experiences and dental care in childhood. Community dentistry and oral epidemiology. Outubro de 2018;46(5):442–8.

Motivo da exclusão: Os "serviços de saúde" identificados no estudo são especificamente os cuidados dentários. O estudo menciona sistemas de prestação de cuidados dentários e o papel dos dentistas na identificação de abuso e negligência infantil, mas não aborda ou detalha outros tipos de serviços de saúde além desse contexto.

4. Deslandes S, Mendes CH, Pinto LW. [Proposal of an index for government measures to deal with domestic violence against children and adolescents]. Cadernos de saúde pública. Agosto de 2015;31(8):1709–20.

Motivo da exclusão: É o enfrentamento a partir da criação de um ÍNDICE e não o enfrentamento dos Serviços de Saúde no contexto da rede intersetorial.

5. Donagh B, Taylor J, Bradbury-Jones C. Service evaluation of an independent domestic violence advocate post in a children's hospital. Nursing children and young people [Internet]. Novembro de 2023; Disponível em: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/37982145/>

Motivo da exclusão: Artigo indisponível na íntegra.

6. Elmquist J, Shorey RC, Febres J, Zapor H, Klostermann K, Schratte A, et al. A review of Children's Advocacy Centers' (CACs) response to cases of child maltreatment in the United States. Aggression Violent Behav. 2015;25:26–34.

Motivo da exclusão: Estudo de revisão da literatura.

7. Gawryszewski VP, Silva MMA da, Malta DC, Mascarenhas MDM, Costa VC, Matos SG e, et al. A proposta da rede de serviços sentinela como estratégia da vigilância de violências e acidentes. *Ciênc Saúde Colet (Impr)*. 2006;11:1269–78.

Motivo da exclusão: Estudo que trata somente da descrição de projetos, protocolos e programas de enfrentamento a violência contra a criança.

8. Hardt NS, Muhamed S, Das R, Estrella R, Roth J. Neighborhood-level hot spot maps to inform delivery of primary care and allocation of social resources. *The Permanente journal*. 2013;17(1):4–9.

Motivo da exclusão: O foco do estudo está voltado para a utilização de mapas para identificar desigualdades em saúde e alocar recursos, achar áreas de maior risco, sem abordar de forma clara e detalhada a atuação dos serviços de saúde especificamente contra a violência doméstica infantil. Não há enfrentamento dos Serviços de Saúde.

9. Henry C. Exposure to domestic violence as abuse and neglect: Constructions of child maltreatment in daily practice. *Child abuse & neglect*. Dezembro de 2018;86:79–88.

Motivo da exclusão: O foco principal do estudo de Colleen Henry é a exposição das crianças à violência doméstica e a maneira como os serviços de proteção à criança nos EUA constroem esse fenômeno como um tipo de maus-tratos em seus registros administrativos, especificamente no contexto dos serviços de bem-estar infantil, e não dos serviços de saúde. Não responde a pergunta da pesquisa.

10. Higgins D, Mathews B, Pacella R, Scott J, Finkelhor D, Meinck F, et al. The prevalence and nature of multi-type child maltreatment in Australia. *Medical Journal of Australia*. Abril de 2023;218:S19–25.

Motivo da exclusão: O estudo não menciona que ele é conduzido por um serviço de saúde que realiza o enfrentamento direto da violência doméstica contra crianças. O estudo é uma pesquisa acadêmica conduzida por várias instituições de ensino e pesquisa, como universidades e centros de pesquisa, e não por um serviço de saúde dedicado ao tratamento ou enfrentamento direto da violência doméstica. Não discute sobre estratégias de enfrentamento pelos serviços de saúde.

11. Howarth E, Feder G, Barter C, Powell C. Harmonising outcome measurement for child focused domestic abuse interventions. Reflections on the development and implementation of a core outcome set. *Frontiers in psychiatry*. 2024;15:1296437.

Motivo da exclusão: Não responde a pergunta da pesquisa.

12. Howarth E, Powell C, Woodman J, Walker E, Chesters H, E S, et al. Protocol for developing core outcome sets for evaluation of psychosocial interventions for children and families with experience or at risk of child maltreatment or domestic abuse. *BMJ open*. Agosto de 2021;11(8):e044431.

Motivo da exclusão: O foco do estudo é o desenvolvimento de um protocolo para avaliar intervenções psicossociais voltadas para famílias e crianças afetadas por violência e maus-

tratos, com a participação de pesquisadores, profissionais e formuladores de políticas. No entanto, ele não detalha o envolvimento direto de serviços de saúde como condutores ou responsáveis pelo estudo. Sem ação de enfrentamento pelos Serviços de Saúde.

13. Ju S, Lee Y. Experiences of family maltreatment by Korean children in Korean National Protective Services. *Child Abuse and Neglect*. 2010;34(1):18–27.

Motivo da exclusão: O cenário da pesquisa aborda crianças que estavam em diferentes tipos de instalações de proteção infantil, incluindo lares de acolhimento, casas coletivas e abrigos temporários, casas de cuidado e lares grupais. Essas instituições foram selecionadas em cinco províncias diferentes da Coreia do Sul, refletindo uma diversidade geográfica no cenário de pesquisa. Sem ação de enfrentamento pelos Serviços de Saúde.

14. Lazenbatt A, Greer J. Safeguarding and protecting children in maternity services: Implications for practice. *Child Care in Practice*. 2009;15(4):313–26.

Motivo da exclusão: O trabalho apresenta estrutura incompleta, com ausência de elementos metodológicos essenciais, seção de resultados e discussão. Apesar de conter introdução e conclusão, o conteúdo se restringe a um debate teórico entre autores, sem o rigor científico necessário.

15. McGilloway S. An evaluation of a wraparound intervention for families whose children are at risk of abuse and/or neglect [Internet]. [citado 12 de setembro de 2025]. Disponível em: <http://www.isrctn.com/ISRCTN13644600>

Motivo da exclusão: O estudo está incompleto, faltam resultados e discussão, além da conclusão.

16. McTavish JR, Chandra PS, Stewart DE, Herrman H, MacMillan HL. Child Maltreatment and Intimate Partner Violence in Mental Health Settings. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* [Internet]. 2022;19(23). Disponível em: <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85143602550&doi=10.3390%2fijerph192315672&partnerID=40&md5=433d792c99c3f70d7488950c02d0807e>

Motivo da exclusão: O texto aborda diferentes aspectos do enfrentamento da violência contra a criança, mas sem focar ações de enfrentamento pelos Serviços de Saúde diretamente.

17. Moore CG, Probst JC, Tompkins M, Cuffe S, Martin AB. The prevalence of violent disagreements in US families: Effects of residence, race/ethnicity, and parental stress. *Pediatrics*. 2007;119:S68–76.

Motivo da exclusão: O estudo utilizou dados da *National Survey of Children's Health* de 2003, não foi conduzido diretamente em um cenário de serviços de saúde específicos, como hospitais ou clínicas. Em vez disso, a pesquisa foi realizada por meio de entrevistas telefônicas nacionais com os pais, e os dados foram coletados para avaliar indicadores de saúde física, emocional e comportamental das crianças. Portanto, o cenário de pesquisa não foi um serviço de saúde, mas sim uma pesquisa domiciliar nacional.

18. Nabors L, Baker-Phibbs C, Woodson K. Community-based counselors' interventions for elementary school-age children coping with trauma. *Journal of prevention & intervention in the community*. 2016;44(2):79–91.

Motivo da exclusão: Os serviços de saúde mental descritos no estudo foram realizados em centros comunitários e em escolas.

19. Nakphong MK, von Ehrenstein OS. Intimate partner violence and childhood illnesses in Cambodia: a cross-sectional study. *Archives of disease in childhood*. Março de 2020;105(3):223–8.

Motivo da exclusão: O estudo não especifica diretamente o tipo de serviço de saúde em que as mães e crianças receberam cuidados. O cenário de pesquisa foi baseado em dados populacionais coletados por Pesquisa Demográfica e de Saúde (CDHS), uma pesquisa nacional representativa, conduzida em ambientes domiciliares, e não vinculada diretamente a um serviço de saúde específico.

20. O'Malley DM, Kelly PJ, Cheng AL. Family violence assessment practices of pediatric ED nurses and physicians. *Journal of emergency nursing*. Maio de 2013;39(3):273–9.

Motivo da exclusão: Estudo de revisão da literatura

21. Pallansch J, Milam C, Manning J, Lewis M, Salzman J, Kopec K. COVID-19 effects on intimate partner violence, sexual assault, and child abuse in the emergency department. *Acad Emerg Med*. 2021;28:S243.

Motivo da exclusão: Estudo indisponível na íntegra.

22. Reichenheim M, Dias A, Moraes C. Co-occurrence of physical violence against partners and their children in health services. *Revista de Saude Publica*. Agosto de 2006;40(4):595–603.

Motivo da exclusão: Sem ação de enfrentamento pelos Serviços de Saúde.

23. Russell A, Clements K, Duschinsky R, Howarth E, Mayes T, Reisel A, et al. Domestic violence and abuse in local child safeguarding policy: How is the problem represented? *Health & social care in the community*. Novembro de 2022;30(6):e3871–84.

Motivo da exclusão: O foco do estudo é a representação da violência doméstica e abuso nas políticas locais de proteção infantil, utilizando a abordagem de *Bacchi* para analisar como o problema é representado nas políticas. Não inclui os serviços de saúde e redes interstoriais e sim somente documentos que falam sobre as políticas.

24. Tan GKY, Symons M, Fitzpatrick J, Connor SG, Cross D, Pestell CF. Adverse childhood experiences, associated stressors and comorbidities in children and youth with fetal alcohol spectrum disorder across the justice and child protection settings in Western Australia. *BMC pediatrics*. Outubro de 2022;22(1):587.

Motivo da exclusão: O objetivo do estudo é explorar as experiências adversas na infância e os estressores associados em crianças e jovens com Transtorno do Espectro Alcoólico Fetal. Sem ação de enfrentamento pelos Serviços de Saúde.

25. Thackeray JD, Scribano PV, Rhoda D. Domestic violence assessments in the child advocacy center. *Child Abuse and Neglect*. 2010;34(3):172–82.

Motivo da exclusão: O foco está na prática de avaliação dentro dos Centros de Advocacia Infantil (CACs), e não na análise dos serviços de saúde em um contexto intersetorial mais amplo.

26. Viswanathan M, Rains C, Hart LC, Doran E, Sathe N, Hudson K, et al. Primary Care Interventions to Prevent Child Maltreatment: Evidence Report and Systematic Review for the US Preventive Services Task Force. *JAMA*. 2024;331(11):959–71.

Motivo da exclusão: Estudo de revisão da literatura.

27. Waldfogel J. Prevention and the child protection system. *Future Child*. 2009;19(2):195–210.

Motivo da exclusão: Compilação do autor revisão. O estudo não apresenta uma população específica de participantes com amostras, pois não foi realizado em um ambiente com coleta direta de dados empíricos. Em vez disso, a análise se baseia em dados administrativos e relatórios de agências de proteção à criança nos Estados Unidos da América, examinando os serviços preventivos oferecidos pelo CPS para famílias em risco de maus-tratos infantis.

28. Whitson M, Bernard S, Kaufman J. The Mediating Role of Parenting Stress for Children Exposed to Trauma: Results from a School-Based System of Care. *Journal of Child & Family Studies*. Abril de 2015;24(4):1141–51.

Motivo da exclusão: Crianças maiores que 12 anos.

29. Wilson D, Koziol-McLain J, Garrett N, Sharma P. A hospital-based child protection programme evaluation instrument: A modified Delphi study. *Int J Qual Health Care*. 2010;22(4):283–93.

Motivo da exclusão: Sem ação de enfrentamento pelos Serviços de Saúde.

30. Yamaoka Y, Hosozawa M, Sampei M, Sawada N, Okubo Y, K T, et al. Abusive and positive parenting behavior in Japan during the COVID-19 pandemic under the state of emergency. *Child abuse & neglect*. Outubro de 2021;120:105212.

Motivo da exclusão: O estudo não identifica explicitamente quais são os serviços de saúde utilizados.

APÊNDICE III – INSTRUMENTO DE EXTRAÇÃO DE DADOS

Detalhes da revisão do escopo	
Título da revisão de escopo:	
Objetivo(s) da revisão:	
Revise as perguntas:	
Critérios de inclusão/exclusão	
População	
Conceito	
Contexto	
Tipos de fonte de evidência	
Detalhes e características da fonte de evidências	
Detalhes da citação (por exemplo, autor(es), data, título, periódico, volume, número, páginas)	
País	
Contexto	
Participantes (detalhes, por exemplo, idade/sexo e número)	
Detalhes/Resultados extraídos da fonte de evidência (em relação ao conceito da revisão de escopo)	
Por exemplo, domínios de qualidade de vida avaliados	
Por exemplo, número de itens na ferramenta	
Por exemplo, detalhes da validação psicométrica da ferramenta	

APÊNDICE IV – REFERÊNCIAS DOS ESTUDOS INCLUÍDOS NA REVISÃO DE ACORDO COM O NOME DO AUTOR

1. Apostólico MR, Hino P, Egry EY. As possibilidades de enfrentamento da violência infantil na consulta de enfermagem sistematizada. *Rev Esc Enferm USP*. 2013;47:320-7. doi:10.1590/S0080-62342013000200007. (D14)
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**APÊNDICE V – INSTRUMENTO PARA AVALIAÇÃO INICIAL DOS
CRITÉRIOS DE INCLUSÃO E EXCLUSÃO – ADAPTADO DE JBI**

Decisão: Incluído Excluído Indeterminado

Título do estudo: _____ Cod. Estudo: _____

Autores: _____ País do estudo: _____ Ano: _____

Revisor: _____

Data: __/__/__

CrITÉrios:

CRITÉRIOS	SIM	NÃO	INDETERMINADO
O estudo aborda os limites e as potencialidades dos serviços de saúde			
O estudo aborda o enfrentamento da violência doméstica contra crianças?			
Desenvolvido no contexto da rede intersetorial?			

APÊNDICE VI – VERSÕES ORIGINAIS DAS CITAÇÕES EM LÍNGUA ESTRANGEIRA

- i. The results indicate that all cases referred to the RCCAN were investigated and families were offered support or existing support was continued or intensified. The support was generally sufficient and well monitored according to the families and professionals involved. Some results were remarkable.
- ii. In Manitoba, government policy as part of the Families First (FF) program is for public health nurses to screen families with newborns within one week post-delivery for a number of risk factors (e.g., maternal young age, financial difficulties, mental health problems, substance use, birth outcomes) associated with adverse child developmental outcomes.
- iii. Health care providers could benefit from additional training to move beyond identification of the typical signs of abuse and neglect to recognize a child in danger or distress (e.g., those presenting with urinary tract infections could have a history of sexual trauma).
- iv. The purpose of the visits is: structured behavioral changes, health education, discussing questions of the expectant mother, setting and maintaining realistic and achievable goals, increasing the mother's self-efficacy and involving the social network of the mother into the program.
- v. The frequency and content of their home-visiting is directed by the needs of the families and continued maximally until the first birthday of the child.
- vi. Safe Care is a home visiting program that provides evidence-based training for parents of young children aged 0–5 who have either been reported for child maltreatment or exhibit risk factors for abuse and neglect.
- vii. The results of this study indicate that an educational program, integrated into the primary care visit, can affect parents' attitudes toward using less physical punishment in the short-term. Given the association between physical punishment, child abuse, and many other adverse consequences, these results have implications for how to improve primary care services, child abuse prevention, and violence prevention.

- viii. These elements included: (a) supportive care, in which the nurse served as an available, interested, and empathic listener; (b) anticipatory guidance, in which the women were told what to expect if the woman decided to access abuse intervention services, as well as the risks associated with leaving the abuser, having the abuser arrested, or applying for a protection order, and (c) guided referrals, in which the nurse offered referrals tailored to the woman's needs, for example, job training and housing. The case management sessions lasted, on average, 20 minutes and women were encouraged to contact the nurse as often as the woman choose.
- ix. Routine abuse assessment and referral have the potential to positively improve the behavioral functioning of children exposed to domestic violence.
- x. The protocol has a high positive predictive value of 91% and can substantially increase the detection rate of child abuse in an ED setting. Parental characteristics are strong predictors of child abuse. Implementing guidelines to detect child abuse based on parental characteristics of parents attending the adult section of the ED can increase the detection rate of child abuse and neglect allowing appropriate aid to be initiated for these families.
- xi. Without the appropriate skill set and training, the accrual of evidence was challenging.
- xii. Interviews revealed widespread lack of training in child abuse, an absence of hospital protocol in managing child abuse presentations, and no child protection officer role either within the hospital or in the community.
- xiii. Health care providers could benefit from additional training to move beyond identification of the typical signs of abuse and neglect to recognize a child in danger or distress [...] Training and public service messages that focus on trauma-informed care would educate health care providers in identification of non typical symptoms, referral procedures for children affected, and ways to engage children and families in care.
- xiv. Lack of formal program evaluation procedures at the hospital may have contributed to the perception that implementing universal screening would overtax the hospital's social work resources. Insufficient staff training may have contributed to personal discomfort in addressing IPV, as well as lack of confidence that colleagues would respond appropriately to a disclosure. A lack of training processes or mandates at the institutional level resulted in sporadic and infrequent staff IPV education. Lack of training also meant those program components that did not need improvement (eg, a

robust response for staff experiencing IPV, established security response to IPV, and IPV advocate availability 24 hours daily) were not well known and subsequently underused.

- xv. El pediatra debe estar capacitado para el abordaje multidisciplinario de los casos que incluye la detección en todos los niveles, la atención integral, pautas claras de manejo y conocimientos acerca de los instrumentos legales nacionales e internacionales; además de estar familiarizado con los indicadores verbales, conductuales y físicos del maltrato; éstos indicadores son vitales para reducir al mínimo las consecuencias para el niño y poner en marcha cuanto antes los servicios necesarios.
- xvi. The Reporting Centers for Child abuse and Neglect (RCCAN) is a federal rather than judicial organization and has the ability to refer children to Child Protective Services (CPS) when necessary. This referral is made when serious measures are required, for example, when children are in danger or when parents consistently shun cooperation with the RCCAN.
- xvii. La conformación de un equipo multidisciplinario permitió aumentar 17 veces la capacidad de efectuar el diagnóstico.
- xviii. Another facilitating factor cited by the Emergency departments professionals (n = 4) concerned the feedback letter describing the assessment and support offered by the Reporting Centers for Child abuse and Neglect (RCCAN) following a referral, which was considered an incentive for continued use of the protocol.
- xix. Because laws pertaining to exposure to domestic violence are just emerging, states will need guidance in developing definitions and procedural criteria for their handbooks or manuals. A clear and comprehensive set of guidelines is needed to reduce uncertainty and increase consistency in decision making and insure that caregivers are treated fairly regardless of their gender. Moreover, a set of decision making criteria could prevent subsequent harm to victims of battering and their children.
- xx. It is not uncommon for each social worker to handle more than 100 cases annually. Such an overload has been associated with a substantial number of maltreatment occurrence after Child Guidance Centers (CGC) involvement, which is an issue of a great public concern. A more sophisticated assessment method is required to prevent adverse incidents.

- xxi. As school nurses I see quite a few children as well and you know as when they want it. They can either come to a drop in, or we can set up some one-to-one meetings. But I mean I'm not a counsellor. But I think sometimes just to be there and just caring and being there to listen sometimes helps. And assess them and refer on. If you can find a suitable agency to refer on to. (School nurse).
- xxii. This finding may represent a reluctance of midwives to discuss the topic of domestic and child abuse with their clients, arising, in many cases, from fears and anxieties about causing offence, of revealing something that may escalate out of control, of not knowing what to do if abuse is disclosed, of embarrassment, or at a personal level, of the identification with abuse either as a victim or perpetrator.
- xxiii. Childhood IPV exposure is also associated with increased health care use and costs. As adults, children exposed to IPV are at increased risk for physical and mental health problems, intergenerational cycles of violence, and decreased occupational achievement and net worth.
- xxiv. Healthcare providers should be mindful that mothers may not disclose violence for fear of their child being removed. Midwives need to be aware of the safety implications for the mother and existing children if she discloses violence.
- xxv. Two main barriers prevented mothers from seeking or accepting support for their children: fear of professional intervention and fear of the perpetrator. Fear of professional intervention was a significant barrier for mothers. Advocate educator (AEs) who provided support and advocacy highlighted that mothers were often concerned that intervention might mean that their child would be removed from their care.
- xxvi. Child witnesses to interparental violence have higher rates of anxiety, conduct disorder, property crime and alcohol abuse/dependence in adolescence. Worse outcomes for child witnesses are seen when violence is more frequent or intense, though gender and age do not appear to consistently affect outcome. Children living in the home may also be emotionally abused. Child physical abuse and partner abuse co-occur in 30% to 60% of cases. It therefore makes clinical sense to assess for child abuse if partner abuse is identified and vice versa (dual assessment).
- xxvii. Children of mothers screening positive for IPV around the time of delivery had significantly increased odds of being diagnosed with attention deficit-hyperactivity

disorder (AOR = 1.86, 99 % CI = 1.06–3.27), lower respiratory tract infections (AOR = 1.53, 99 % CI = 1.21–1.93), and to have been hospitalized for an injury (AOR = 2.00, 99 % CI = 1.14–3.51) in the 5-years after birth than children born to mothers screening negative for IPV.

- xxviii. The results from this study suggest that the COVID-19 pandemic, social distancing, school and daycare closures, and subsequent economic downturn have heightened the risk of child maltreatment in already vulnerable- and predominantly low income-families with young children according to providers who deliver parenting services. This evidence is crucial for understanding how at-risk caregivers and children been affected by an unprecedented public health emergency and for considering policy and public health responses in the case of future pandemics and emergency situations.
- xxix. Currently, there are missed opportunities for identification and for intervention with respect to psychological trauma exposure in children seeking services within the Emergency departments (ED) setting, which may be due in part to current screening practices.
- xxx. Families are discussed every 3months to ensure that providers are not duplicating services and are communicating effectively regarding clients' needs. Biannual celebrations recognize accomplishments of the treatment families.
- xxxi. Only half of the parents indicated that they were well informed about the procedure. This is an important finding: it is possible that some ED professionals give unclear or incomplete information. This means that it could be advisable to give parents an explanatory brochure explaining the procedure.
- xxxii. In total, 23 participants took part in the focus groups including health staff (school nurses, midwife, health visitors), education staff (link teachers and educational support staff including learning mentors, parent support worker and education welfare officers), family support and early years workers, and specialist support staff (Family Intervention Project workers and an Independent Domestic Violence Advocate).
- xxxiii. The number of patients covered by the Protocol's guidelines who attended the ED in the years after implementation remained very high and actually increased annually [...] Possibly, the increase may be the result of the increased vigilance of ED professionals concerning implementation of the new Protocol.

- xxxiv. [...] No formal routine for in-depth trauma screening was applied at the agencies. [...] Missing data due to non-responses were few and were considered randomly distributed. [...] Seven (14%) mother-child dyads discontinued the intervention and did not provide post-treatment or follow-up data. [...] No formal measure of attendance was applied.
- xxxv. [...] recommended involving subjects or the target community in planning interventions, taking care that interventions are ethnically and culturally appropriate.
- xxxvi. The Spanish public health system has support services for battered women, but as this was not the reason for the clinical consultation, information regarding the specific treatment services that is provided to caregivers was not made available to the researchers. [...] findings show the need to develop effective preventive and therapeutic interventions for children and their families; clinicians and other health professionals could activate protective resources (individual, social or legal) to minimize the negative impact of violence.
- xxxvii. Chart review to assess documentation practices, as no patient care area routinely documented IPV screening results.
- xxxviii. Documentation of suspicions, conversations with colleagues, or accompanying data such as psychological assessment, the family environment, and interactions are perceived as inappropriate and thus not routinely practiced.
- xxxix. The hospital scored 17 of 100 points on the Delphi instrument assessment. Key areas of weakness identified by the Delphi instrument and interviews included lack of coordinated provider training and evaluation of IPV-related processes and no standards for IPV screening, safety assessment, and documentation.
- xl. To understand which criteria were applied to the batterers versus the victims of battering and to determine whether gender bias occurred, each person was assigned to one of eight possible groups, based on who the investigator thought was the batterer and the victim of battering, his or her gender, and who the investigator substantiated for the child's exposure.
- xli. Racial/ethnic minorities are disproportionately impacted by poverty, COVID-19, and child maltreatment, and these factors may interact at family, neighborhood, and community levels. [...] No questions about age or gender were asked in the survey.

- xlii. One in five children had a maltreatment allegation following their mother's hospitalisation for assault. This increased to two in five children when the mother was assaulted in the prenatal period. Aboriginal children accounted for 57.6% of all allegations despite representing only 7.8% of the population.
- xliii. [...] many important risk and protective factors (e.g., parental education, access to early childhood education programs, social support, race/ethnicity, house hold income) were unavailable in the data.
- xliv. [...] most stakeholders identified as White, and only 22% were Black or Hispanic. This lack of diversity may have decreased the cultural responsiveness of the recommendations provided in this study and propagate unintended consequences of routine evaluations that differentially impact children of color.
- xlv. Building Healthy Children (BHC) serves families residing in Rochester, New York, an ethnically and racially diverse area (population 16.4% Latino, 41.7% black, and 43.7% white, 2010 US Census). [...] Assigned outreach workers reflective of the ethnicity and culture of BHC participants provide a consistent, nurturing relationship that helps retain families in the program and readies parents for the evidence-based treatments, movement toward goals, and behavior change. Outreach workers help to stabilize families and ensure compliance with medical appointments and recommended care.
- xlvi. [...] recommended involving subjects or the target community in planning interventions, taking care that interventions are ethnically and culturally appropriate.